

A Study on Investors' Perception on Futures Trading On Water with Special Reference to Kerala State

Ms. Sruthi Sreenivasan¹, Mr. Sreekanth S².

¹Assistant Professor, Tharanellur Arts and Science College, Irinjalakuda.

²Research Scholar

Corresponding author- **Ms. Sruthi Sreenivasan**

Email-Sreesruthi16@gmail.com

Abstract

This study focuses on the investor's perception on futures trading on the necessity commodity water. It is a new opportunity that the investors or hedgers can enter in to a future contract on water. It will bring a drastic change in the derivatives market. Water is the most essential element and commodity for the livelihood of human beings and all living species. There is and will not be any life on the earth without water. Even though, due to do the exploitation and excess use of water, it becomes limited in availability. The earth is almost filled with 70% of water. But the pure water is lacking. Pollution, Industrial use of water, climatic conditions and miserable human activities can cause water exploitation. By anticipating drought and lack of sufficiency of water in future, nowadays it made possible to enter into future contract on water. The speciality of Kerala is that this state gets abundance of rain during rainy season and facing drastic drought during peak summer season. Hence it gives more focus to water conservation. Likewise, Kerala has plenty of investors and the state is also characterised by high rate of literacy. Thus, they are aware about the investment opportunities and flexible enough to take risks.

Keywords: Future contract, Investor perception, water exploitation, Industrial use of water.

Introduction

Investors are always questing for new investment opportunities. Futures and option contracts are gaining more importance nowadays. One of the innovations in futures contract trading is water futures. From 7th December 2020, one can enter into water futures which will allow traders, investors, or hedgers to buy or sell water contracts like any other commodities like oil, gold etc. Chicaco Mercantile Exchange group Introduced H20: Nasdac Veles California Water Index which is noted as NQH2O to give base to water futures. Even during the time of COVID 19 pandemic, speculators found it as a way to make profit. A water futures contract is a contract between two counterparties that allows to trade or deal with specific quantity and quality of water at a specific and predetermined expiry date. It found that the standard expiry year is 20. In the nearest future, the scarcity of water will increase the scope of water futures.

Analysis

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the investors' perception on futures trading on water.
2. To analyse the whether there is any relationship between investor's age and water future trading.
3. To understand the level of awareness of investors on water futures.

Hypothesis

H₀ - There is no significant relationship between age and investment level in water futures.

H₁ - There is significant relationship between age and investment level in water futures.

Research Methodology

Descriptive research design is used in the study. Sample size is 50. Purposive sampling method has been followed for collecting responses from respondents. Both primary and secondary data is used for data collection. Primary data is collected through questionnaire and secondary data is collected through websites, journals, books, magazines and newspapers.

Table 1.1 Ages

Age of investors	Percentage
Less than 30	28
30 – 50	40
More than 50	32

Interpretation: From the above table, we can interpret that, most of the respondents are form the age group 30 years to 50 years.

Table 1.2 Awareness on water futures

Category	Percentage
Highly Aware	36
Moderately aware	64
Nothing at all	0

Interpretation: From the above table, it is clear that all respondents are aware about the water futures. More than half percentage of the respondents are

highly aware of it and some of them are moderately aware.

Table 1.3 investors' perception on purpose water futures

Category	Percentage
For hedging the risk of water scarcity in future	40
For making profits	40
For arbitrage process	10
For other purposes	10

Interpretation: We can interpret from the above table that people are making use of water futures

mainly for hedging the risk of water scarcity in future and for making profits.

Table 1.4 Opinion on age as a factor for choosing water futures

Category	Percentage
To a great extent	40
To a small extent	40
Never	20

Interpretation: From the above table, it is clear that age is an important factor for entering into the future contract. Even though, some people do not consider age as a factor.

Conclusion

Water futures are an innovative instrument for hedging the risk of scarcity of water in future period. Investors use this instruments as tool for hedging or for making profits through price changes and speculation. Almost all investors are aware about this new development in derivative trading. Which gives a light that this step will create a dramatic and drastic changes in coming era. Most of the people consider their current age as a factor for choosing the contract. Young people can move forward with a long-term futures contract. But senior citizens are getting confused on their life expectancy and always take a risk averse and short term investment decision. In short, the life expectancy of people will affect the investment decisions in water futures trading. Hence, It is clear that H_1 is proven.

Nowadays, Derivative instruments are getting popular than equity trading, there is a possibility that investors in age group less than 30 will eventually increase.

Suggestions

1. Awareness campaigns and schemes should be conducted to improve the knowledge on scope of water futures.

2. Water futures with shorter maturity period can be invented to make the aged population more comfortable.
3. in India, Derivative training is in the growing stage. So, there should be efforts and ways to develop water futures along with other derivative instruments.
4. Water futures trading can be made available in online trading platforms and thereby it can be reach to wider audience.

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